

Supplementary Figures for Waterbird foraging traces from the Early Eocene Green River Formation, Utah by John-Paul Zonneveld, Sarah Naone and Brooks Britt

Figure S1. Specimen BYU 50695. 5.1. Photograph of the plate showing three indeterminate, apparently palmate footprints in association with a sinuous trend of connected pits connected by a long groove consistent with *Erevnoichnus blochi*. 5.2. Whitened enlargement of the portion of the BYU 50695 plate hosting the sinuous specimen of *Erevnoichnus blochi*.

Figure S2. Specimen BYU 50697. S2.1. Photograph of the entire plate illustrating numerous distinct *Presbyornithiformipes feducii* footprints preserved in convex hyporelief. Five of these footprints comprise a trackway that traverses the slab from bottom left to top right. Other footprints traverse the slab from centre right to centre bottom, indicating either that the bird reversed direction to the right of the preserved slab, or that another bird walked in an opposite direction. A sinuous trend of foraging traces assigned to *Erevnoichnus blochi* meanders back and forth across the trackway to the top-right edge of the plate (segments 1a, 1b and 1c). A second sinuous trend meanders back onto, and off again, the right edge of the plate (segments 2a and 2b). Arrows denote the direction of behavioural movement of each segment. S2.2. Closeup of the portion of plate BYU 50697 with the two *E. blochi* segments.

Figure S3. Photograph of BYU 50699 showing a complete right *Presbyornithiformipes feducii* footprint in association with a highly sinuous pit trend consistent with *Erevnoichnus strimmerna* and a partial *P. feducii* footprint on the left edge of the image. The arrows show the progressive movement of the tracemaker from left to right.

Figure S4. Photograph of BYU 50696 with one complete and one partial *P. feducii* footprint in association with a mildly sinuous pit trend consistent with *Erevnoichnus blochi*. The arrows show the direction of trace emplacement. Note that it is unlikely that footprints on this slab are related to the specimen of *E. blochi* on this plate as they are inconsistent in orientation relative to the *E. blochi* trace when compared with all other specimens.

Figure S5. Additional specimens of *Erevnoichnus blochi* associated with *Presbyornithiformipes feducii*. S5.1. Photograph of BYU 50946 with 15 mounds between several *P. feducii* footprints. This specimen is preserved in convex hyporelief and appears to comprise an overtrack surface, emplaced a mm or more above the occupation horizon. S5.2. Photograph of BYU 50947 with 23 mounds between several *P. feducii* footprints. The trend of the mounds is interrupted by the trace-maker's footprints. This specimen is preserved in convex hyporelief and appears to comprise an overtrack surface, emplaced a mm or more above the occupation horizon.





10 cm

*Erevnoichnus strimmena*

*Erevnoichnus strimmena*

ii

iii

i

iv

mudcrack

*Presbyorniformipes feducii*



2.

10 cm



*Erevnoichnus blochi*

mudcrack

ii

L1

i

R1

iii

*Presbyorniformipes feducii*

iv

mudcrack

1.



2.

